

PRINCIPLES OF FORMING SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN GRADUATE CLASS STUDENTS BASED ON GENDER APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10617204>

Annotation: In this thesis, considerations are made about the principles of organization based on the gender approach in the formation of social and cultural competence in the students of the graduating class.

Key words: Education system, gender approach, attitude culture, sociology, cultural studies.

Introduction:

Pedagogical education in Uzbekistan has been undergoing a period of formation in recent years, which is aimed at bringing it into line with the requirements adopted in the European Union countries. In connection with the modernization of the higher school, the revision of the content for teachers in connection with the adoption of tertiary education standards, new requirements for the development of a set of programs and the organization of the entire educational process of students, general cultural, general professional, professional and special competence aimed at training specialists

The formation of the theory of the gender approach is considered by the foreign and Uzbek scientific community as one of the most important elements of the modern modernization of education, because researchers show that the modern researcher and teacher in the field of humanitarian and social knowledge, including pedagogical education It is impossible to prepare without the teaching of theory, because it has been a professional norm in fields that have long developed with the change of scientific knowledge and the study of socio-cultural phenomena without taking into account the gender factor all social institutions, cultural norms and values, methodologists are considered wrong. In this regard, the analysis of the practical conditions for the study of the theory of gender approach in parent pedagogical education is contradictory and is characterized by their insignificance.

Published official recommendations on the study of the foundations of gender knowledge in the educational system, including the introduction of training programs for the improvement of the quality of correction and professional re-planning for management personnel, teachers and teachers, gender special courses on learning the basics of knowledge, gender policy, methods of gender approach in management, processes. It is, unfortunately, limited to the list of official documents of the last decades, although in European

countries (*Germany, France*) a comprehensive database has been created in the last two decades, it has its own It continues to be updated with specific gender issues and proposals for their solution, and in Finland and Scandinavia, gender issues are at the center of public policy and have a positive impact on the development of gender approach theory in education¹.

Gender as a socio-cultural phenomenon developed by society, manifested in differences in male and female roles, behavior, mental and emotional characteristics, is one of the methods of social stratification of society, a system of social but constructed inequality based on gender. Socio-demographic factors such as gender and race, ethnicity, class and age constitute the overall system of social hierarchy. Gender issues are interdisciplinary and are studied by specialists of various disciplines (sociology, cultural studies, history, philology, psychology, pedagogy)². All gender knowledge is built on the basis of the main ideas of the worldview, the gene of the soda approach is to build a civil society in Uzbekistan, to develop and strengthen democratic ideas and views in our country. With the development of democracy and the spread of the principles of an open society, one of the most important socio-cultural tasks is to overcome all types of discrimination and suppress the free development of the individual, including gender.

The gender course in education aims to promote the skills of analyzing the social reality and individual experience of men and women in order to eliminate the consequences of the unfair classification of men and women and their unequal status. In the context of our research, the gender category is important as a characteristic of the social-pedagogical order, which is constantly reflected in various social institutions, directly in the teaching process, professional-pedagogical interaction and it is repeated and improved in the process of scientific research. The main goal of the theory of gender course in pedagogical education is to study the laws of formation and development of personality characteristics of a future teacher as a representative of a certain gender and its students, to clarify the ways and methods of achieving gender equality.

Implementation of the gender approach in education is a condition for deconstructing traditional cultural restrictions, developing the potential of a person regardless of gender, maximizing self-awareness and revealing the abilities of students in the educational process includes the creation and creation of a university that contributes to equal pedagogic interaction, which is

¹ Kamenskaya E. N. Gender approach to pedagogy: abstract. dis. ... Dr. ped. Sci. Rostov n/d., 2006.

² Гендерная экспертиза учебников для высшей школы / под. ред. О.А. Ворониной. М., 2005.

the conditions for the growth of self-awareness with a characteristic set. Among the priorities of modern pedagogical education is the humanization of all its fields, from the point of view of gender pedagogical research, it is, first of all, to approach reality from the point of view of maturity of men and women and in the name of the development of a whole personality in each of them. At the same time, it is an attempt to see the world in terms of gender. Gender disciplines are taught in the educational process, but only recently. The main content of the topic of gender is related to the idea of affirming the rights and opportunities for self-realization. Mastering the basics of gender knowledge is consistent with the main goals of modernizing higher education and improving the quality of education.

The tasks of the sciences: to form a system of knowledge in students about the social and scientific conditions of the idea of gender education, the essence of modern approaches to the interpretation of the categories "gender education", "equality relations", "culture of gender relations".

The essence of the gender approach in education, the development of the ability to combine psychological and pedagogical knowledge about the trends of gender culture in modern society, gender culture, pedagogical to solve the practical problems of gender education and upbringing based on modern technologies of gender education of students acquire the experience of implementing gender strategies of organizing the process.

Researchers distinguish gender competence, including the individual style of the teacher, the gender difference, which allows the future teacher to not be the subject and object of situations of gender inequality, to resist discriminatory influences and influences; to have an idea about the purpose of men and women in society, their complexion, functions and characteristics of relationships, professional interaction. Each teacher is a source of information, has a unique style of presenting educational material, serves as a carrier of a certain gender section. Students are distinguished by certain gender characteristics, so the most important task of universities should be to create an environment of demand for gender culture of teachers and students.

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